

3E11 A new ignitable spark detection system for lightning protection in CFRP structure

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Abstract

In the aircraft structure design, a demonstration of fuel tank ignition prevention by lightning is required by FAA regulation § 25.981. The demonstrations required by this regulation are very tough and many tests are spent. Demonstrations are confirmed a detection of sparks by a lightning test using fuel tank coupon specimens or fuel system components. Usually detection of spark is took a photograph by digital camera. However, detection of sparks from photographs is requires a large number of test and judgment times. This research aims to reduce tests and judgment times, and reports on the development of the automatic spark detection system using optical sensors instead of digital camera.

In digital cameras, dispersion of spark brightness is large even with the same energy spark..

In order to confirm safety, it is necessary to conduct many tests and perform statistical processing.

Spark Light measurement by a Digital Camera

The PMT measurement is highly accurate and it is possible to greatly reduce the number of tests. And more, it is unnecessary to make a judgment after the test like photo judgment.

It greatly reduces the development time.

Spark Light measurement by a PMT